

Quinoline Derivatives : Part XXI.**Synthesis of Some 8-Hydroxyquinoline Derivatives as Possible Amoebicidal or Trypanocidal Agents

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Starting from 8-hydroxyquinoline, the synthesis of different azaheterocyclic derivatives were reported from this laboratory some of which exhibit significant amoebicidal activity¹⁻³. Since some iodo derivatives and Mannich bases⁴ of 8-hydroxyquinoline possess definite antiamebic property, our earlier work has been extended in that line of approach.

In the present work, we have utilised three intermediates namely 8-hydroxy-5-(2', 5'-dimethyl pyrrol-1')-quinoline²-(A), 2-[(8'-hydroxy quinolyl-5') methyl]-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline⁵ (B) and 6-hydroxy-1, 7-phenanthroline⁶ (C) which were earlier synthesised in this laboratory. The method of synthesis of the third compound viz. phenanthroline derivative (C) has been further modified whereby the ease and yield of the reaction has been improved.

The desired iodo derivatives (I-III) have been prepared from the respective hydroxyquinoline

derivatives (A-C) by the action of iodine monochloride on the ethanolic solution of the base. On the other hand the Mannich bases (IV) and (V) have been obtained by reacting the ethanolic solution of the corresponding bases (A) and (C) with 1, 2, 3, 4, tetrahydroisoquinoline⁶,⁷ and piperidine hydrochloride respectively in presence of paraformaldehyde. The physico-chemical characteristics of these compounds have been recorded (Vide *experimental*).

Experimental

All melting points recorded are uncorrected. UV absorption spectrum was taken in ethanol solution and measured in a Hilger Spectrophotometer, model H700, using quartz cells. IR spectra were recorded on Beckman IR-8 spectrophotometer on KBr disc.

7-Iodo-8-hydroxy-5-(2', 5'-dimethylpyrrol-1')-quinoline (I) :

A solution of compound (A ; 2.06 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated under stirring in a water bath at 55°. To that solution was added dropwise iodine monochloride (1.9 g) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) and the stirring was continued for 1 hr, when crystalline precipitate was obtained. The product was cooled and filtered. The residue was triturated with 10% aq. sodium carbonate solution (200 ml), then filtered, washed, made free from alkali and subsequently crystallised from large volume of ethanol to give shining golden yellow needles (3 g).

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NOTES

When heated with conc. sulphuric acid, it evolves copious vapour of iodine. When its chloroform solution is shaken with dilute nitric acid, the chloroform layer slowly turns deep violet and nitric acid turns yellow.

2-[(7'-Iodo-8'-hydroxyquinolyl-5') methyl]-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro iso quinoline (II) :

Starting with Compound (B ; 2.9 g) in ethanol (50 ml) and iodine monochloride (1.75 g) in ethanol (20 ml) and following the same procedure as outlined above, the compound (II) was obtained as a solid product which was crystallised from ethanol in yellowish green microcrystalline powder (1.5 g). It gives usual tests for iodo compound as mentioned in case of (I).

Modified method of preparation of 6-hydroxy-1, 7-phenanthroline (C)

5-Nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline^{9,10,11} (24 g) was taken with anhydrous glycerine (68 ml) in a three necked flask protected from moisture and fitted with a condenser and mechanical stirrer. Acetic acid (46 ml) was added dropwise from a separating funnel and subsequently conc. sulphuric acid (46 ml) was added in a similar manner. Stirring was continued throughout the whole addition which required about 1 hr. After complete addition, the mixture was kept at 160-65° in oil bath for 12 hr under stirring.

Next day the black residue was treated with 10% sulphuric acid (ca 500 ml) and filtered. The filtrate after clarification with charcoal was basified with sodium carbonate solution in cold to afford a dark precipitate which was purified through acid-alkali (HCl-NH₄OH) treatment. The greenish solid thus obtained was extracted with hot ethanol. The ethanolic solution on concentration afforded slender light yellow needles (3 g); m.p. 160° (Lit⁹ m.p. 160-61°). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 232, 276 m μ (log ϵ 4.42, 4.33); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3200 (-OH); 2350, 1620, 1560 (>C=N-and-C=C-); 1475, 1425, 1375, 1330; 1300, 1275, 1235, 1190, 1165 (tert-amine), 1100, 930, 890, 860, 850, 820,

790, 755 (differently substituted benzene ring), 715 cm⁻¹. (Found : N, 14.35. C₁₄H₈ON₂ requires N, 14.28%). Its ethanolic solution gives greenish blue colouration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

The picrate was crystallised from ethanol m.p. 235° (dec) [Lit⁹ 237° (dec.)].

5-Iodo-6-hydroxy-1,7-phenanthroline(III) :

The compound (III) was prepared following the same procedure of (I) from the reaction of compound (C ; 1.9 g) in ethanol (30 ml) with iodine monochloride (2.1 g) in ethanol (25 ml). The resulting compound was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish brown needles (2.5 g).

7-(1', 2', 3', 4'-Tetrahydroisoquinolyl methyl-2')-8-hydroxy-5'-(2', 5-dimethylpyrryl-1')-quinoline(IV) :

To a solution of Compound (A ; 3.98g) in Ethanol (250 ml) was added paraformaldehyde (0.6 g) and 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro isoquinoline^{6,7} (2.85 g). The mixture was heated under reflux for 5 hr and filtered hot. The filtrate was concentrated to afford a dark brown gummy product which on trituration with anhydrous ether furnished a reddish brown solid product. This on acid-alkali (HCl-NH₄OH) purification gave a cream coloured solid which was highly soluble in ethanol, sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in ether. It was crystallised from aq. ethanol in cream coloured micro crystalline powder (2 g).

5-Piperidyl methyl-6-hydroxy-1, 7-phenanthroline(V) :

A mixture of ethanolic solution of Compound (C ; 1.6 g), piperidine hydrochloride (1.1 g) and paraformaldehyde (0.3 g) was heated under reflux and filtered while hot. The filtrate was concentrated to afford a gummy mass which on trituration with acetone gave a greenish solid. The dilute hydrochloric acid solution of this solid product on clarification with charcoal and subsequent basification with ammonia furnished a solid, crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow crystalline powder (1.25 g).

The m.p., analytical and I.R. spectral data of compounds (I-V) have been placed in Table I.

TABLE—1 ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (I—V)

Compound	Mol. formula	m.p. °C	Analyses								$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm ⁻¹
			Required %				Found %				
			C	H	N	I	C	H	N	I	
I	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₂ I	340	—	—	7.68	34.98	—	—	7.39	34.57	3350(OH); 2850, 2350, 2100, 1630, 1600, 1550, 1500. (>C=N & -C=C-) 1480 1425, 1380 (>C-CH ₃) ⁹ ; 1310, 1275, 1260, 1240 1210, 1175; 1150 (tert-amine) 1110, 1075, 1050, 940, 855, 825, 780, 745, 725 cm ⁻¹
II	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON ₂ I	134	—	—	6.72	30.61	—	—	6.48	30.50	—
III	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ I	222	—	—	8.68	39.53	—	—	8.47	39.24	3200(OH); 2350, 1750; 1620, 1580, 1520 (>C=N & -C=C-) 1480, 1440, 1380, 1340, 1300, 1280, 1245, 1200, 1130, 1075, 1025 (tert-amine); 925, 815, 795, 770 cm ⁻¹
IV	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ON ₂	118	78.32	6.52	10.96	—	78.13	6.45	10.79	—	—
V	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON ₂	320	73.72	6.48	14.33	—	73.58	6.32	14.21	—	3200 (-OH); 2350; 1620, 1580, 1560 (>C=N & -C=C-) 1480, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1285; 1270, 1200, 1150, 1125, 1110, (tert-amine) 1075, 1020; 965, 830, 795 & 750 cm ⁻¹

Pharmacology :

In view of the recent report on the trypanocidal activity of some 5, 7-disubstituted 8-hydroxyquinolines⁸, the compounds (IV) were put under pharmacological testing to evaluate whether they possess any amoebicidal and/or trypanocidal activity. From preliminary observations it appears that none of these compounds possesses any appreciable activity against *E. histolytica* and *T. evansi*.

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